

Extraction, Characterization and Evaluation of Health Applications of *Moringa oleifera* Seed Oil

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Abstract:

In this study, the seeds of *Moringa oleifera* (MO) plant grown in the Adamawa Region of Cameroon were valorized by extracting their oil using mechanical expression. The oil was allowed to clarify through by gravity and an oil yield of 26.07% was obtained. The extracted MO oil was subjected to physicochemical characterization giving the following results; the density of the oil was 0.896 g/mL, a refractive index of 1.468, a viscosity of 49.80 ± 0.30 mPa.s, an acid value of 2.69%, a peroxide value of 3.7 meq of O₂/kg of oil, a saponification value of 189.34 mg of KOH/g of oil and an iodine index of 67.79g/100g of oil. The determination of relevant secondary

metabolites by titration revealed a flavonoid content of 0.66 mg GAE/g, total phenol content of 9.7 mg QE/g, carotenoid content of 0.25 mg beta-carotene/g and antioxidant activity gave an IC₅₀ concentration of 17.5 mg/mL. Determination of the fatty acid profile revealed that oleic acid (78.45%) makes up the predominant component in the MO seed oil. The chemical composition of the MO seed oil was further verified by IR spectroscopy whose spectral interpretation revealed a predominance of fatty acid moieties in the oil. From these results, it appears that *Moringa oleifera* seed oil has moisturizing, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and nourishing properties and therefore the oil is a potent raw material or bioactive substance in the formulation of cosmetic products like creams for body lotion to combat skin infections and the MO seed can find pharmaceutical applications amongst others.

Keywords: Valorization, Extraction, Characterization, Secondary metabolites, fatty acid profile, cosmetic formulation.

Introduction

The *Moringa oleifera* (MO), is a plant cultivated in many countries around the world (Sreelatha et al., 2009). In Cameroon, the plant proliferates much more in the Northern Regions where it forms part of the diet of the populations

(Mawouma et al., 2014). Indigenous knowledge and use of *Moringa* is documented in over 80 countries and it is known in over 200 local languages (Arora et al., 2013). MO trees are recognized as an important agricultural crop because many of its parts are edible (Rahman et

al., 2009). Moringa is grown for its nutritious pods, leaves, edible flowers and can be used as food, medicine and cosmetic oil (Vergara-Jimenez et al., 2017). The seeds, on the other hand, have attracted the interest of scientists because Moringa seeds contain a significant amount of oil with a high-quality fatty acid composition. Moringa seed oil is desirable for cosmetics and perfumes due to suitable properties, it is also edible and endowed with medicinal properties (Djaoui et al., 2015). Some medicinal uses of MO include the ability its leaves to stimulate cardiac function and blood circulation and anti-tumor properties (Bukar et al., 2010). Different parts of MO have useful properties such as the leaves and barks which have antibacterial properties (Abalaka et al., 2012). This work is however focused on MO seeds around the Ngaoundere municipality to valorize local species, cross-check plausible existence of chemical polymorphism, oil extraction, characterization and evaluation of pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications.

Materials and Methods

Materials

The plant materials (seeds) used in our study were harvested from the conurbations of the Ngaoundere III geographical area. The Moringa seeds were obtained from the pods and their shells were manually removed. The seeds were dried in the open air for 7 days then kept away from light and humidity, to avoid any oxidative degradation of constituent lipids. Relevant chemicals such as the Wijs reagent, Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazil amongst others and solvents were purchased from Scientific shops dealing with laboratory materials and chemical reagents in the town of Ngaoundere. In this study, relevant equipment used included water bath, electronic balance, refractometer, spectrophotometer, pH meter, magnetic stirrer, hot plate and relevant glassware.

Methods

Extraction of Oil from *Moringa oleifera* Seeds

A mechanical press with a working capacity of 3-5kg/hour, a voltage of 220v/110v, a Motor Power of 400W, a Net weight of 10.5 kg, made of 304# food grade stainless steel and dimensions 370x160x360mm was used to extract MO seed oil. The machine's heating switch was turned on for a time lapse of 10 minutes after which the dry seeds were introduced through the hopper and then the 'Squeezing' switch was activated to begin extraction. During this extraction, the oil was collected from bellow and filtered and the cakes were expelled at the end of the extruder. The pressed oil separated under gravity influence after overnight storage at laboratory temperature. The extraction yield was calculated using the formular earlier employed by Alang et al., (2019).

$$\%Yield = \frac{M_o}{M_s} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (1)$$

Where

M_o , represents the mass of oil extracted and M_s , represents the mass of seeds taken.

Physico-Chemical Characterizations of the Oil

Density

The density of an oil sample determines its conditions of use and storage, including the value and therefore the cost. The density of the oil was determined using the density bottle method. The weight of a 50 mL capacity bottle was measured (M_1), the container was filled with the oil sample and the combined weight was measured (M_2), the measured oil volume (V_i) was been noted. The density of the oil sample was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{(M_2 - M_1)}{V_1} \quad (2)$$

$$Av = \frac{(V \times C \times 56.01)}{M} \quad (3)$$

Viscosity

The viscosity of an oil refers to its resistance to flow. Heavy molecular weight oils have higher viscosities while lighter molecular weight oils have lower viscosities at specified temperatures. The rheological behavior of our oil was determined by measuring the viscosity using a Brookfield HB-DVIII Ultra Rheometer. The oil sample to be analyzed was taken into a clean and dry 250 mL beaker and the viscosity was determined by the standard operating procedure of the viscometer using Spindler No. 3. The latter was used to determine the viscosity of the sample at the rotation speed of 60 rpm for intervals of 30 seconds up to 180 seconds for each measurement. The oil samples were measured at a temperature of $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. By rotating the spindle of a rheometer in an oil sample, viscosity measurements were taken at regular time intervals.

Determination of the Oil Refraction Index

The refractometer prisms were washed with petroleum ether and then wiped with a clean, soft cloth. Then, 2 drops of oil were placed between the prisms. Subsequently, the riflescope was moved so that the line dividing the light range and the dark range was located at the crossroads of the reticle wires. The refractive index of the oil was finally measured at a $T^\circ\text{C} = 20^\circ\text{C}$.

Determination of Acid Number of MO

The acid number is defined as the number of milligrams of KOH necessary to neutralize the acidity of 1 gram of oil. Determining the acidity of extracted oil is a measurement that is of great commercial importance. 1g of oil was weighed in a 250mL conical flask. The test portion was dissolved in 100 mL of the mixture of 1:1 volume of ethanol and ethyl acetate previously neutralized. The mixture was titrated with a 0.1 M ethanolic KOH solution until the pink color of the phenolphthalein persisted for at least 10 seconds. The acid number was then calculated using the relation:

Where;

A_v : Acid number, V : Volume of KOH solution, C : concentration of the KOH and M : mass of the oil

Determination of Peroxide Value

In a conical flask, 2g of oil was weighed then 10 mL of dichloro methane was added. The test portion was quickly dissolved by stirring. Then, 15 mL of acetic acid and 1 mL of KOH solution was added. The cap was quickly replaced and the solution was stirred for one minute and allowed to stand for exactly 5 minutes in the dark at a temperature of 25°C . After this, 75 mL of distilled water was added. The released iodine was titrated with 0.002N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution by stirring vigorously and using starch solution as an indicator. A blank test was carried out alongside the sample test. The peroxide value (P_v), was expressed in milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram using the formula:

$$P_v = \frac{(V \times N \times 1000)}{M} \quad (4)$$

Determination of the Saponification Value of MO Oil

The saponification number of an oil is generally determined using the ASTM D94 analytical method. It is the quantity of KOH in milligrams necessary to saponify 1gram of oil. The saponification value gives an indication of the average molecular weight of the constituent fatty acids in the oil sample. Two grams of oil was weighed in a conical flask. 25 mL of 0.5N alcoholic KOH was added and refluxed. Boiling regulators like glass beads were added to the Erlenmeyer flask. The heating under reflux continued for 30 minutes with occasional stirring. The excess alkali was titrated in the hot soapy solution with 0.5N HCl using the phenolphthalein indicator. A blank test was carried out under the same conditions to titrate the alcoholic KOH solution. The saponification

value (S_v) was computed using the following formula:

$$S_v = \frac{(V_b - V_s) \times C \times 56.01}{m} \quad (5)$$

Where, S_v : Saponification value, V_b : Blank titration volume; V_s : Sample titration volume; C : Titrant concentration (HCl) and m : mass of oil sample taken

Determination of Iodine Value

The iodine value implies the mass in grams of iodine fixed per 100 grams of oil. In this test, 0.1g of MO oil was introduced into a 500 mL flask, 20 mL of solvent was added to dissolve the oil. Subsequently, exactly 25 mL of Wijs' reagent was added. Then, the container was capped, shaken and placed in a dark place for one hour. A blank test was prepared with solvent and reagent but without the test sample. At the end of this time, 20 mL of the KI solution and 150 mL of water were added to each vial. The solution was titrated with a 0.1N $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution using starch as indicator until the yellow color due to iodine had disappeared. A few drops of the starch solution were added and the titration was continued until the blue color disappeared after vigorously shaking of the contents.

The Iodine Value (I_v) was calculated using the formula earlier used by Alang et al., (2018) as follows:

$$I_v = \frac{[V_1 - V_2] \times 12.96 \times C}{m} \quad (6)$$

Where;

I_v : Iodine Value.

C : Concentration, in moles per liter, of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution used.

V_1 : Volume, in milliliters, of the $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution used for the blank test.

V_2 : Volume, in milliliters, of the $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ solution used for the test sample

m : mass, in grams, of the test sample.

Assays of Total Soluble Phenols

The determination of total polyphenols was carried out using the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric reagent. All phenolic compounds are oxidized by the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. This reagent is yellowish composed of a mixture of phosphotungstic acid ($\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$) and phosphomolybdic acid ($\text{H}_3\text{PMO}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$). These acids are reduced during oxidation of phenols to give a mixture of blue oxides of tungsten and molybdenum. The intensity of the blue color produced, measured by a UV-Visible Spectrophotometer is proportional to the number of phenolic compounds which absorb maximally at 765 nm (Ojeil et al., 2010). In this study, Na_2CO_3 was added to accelerate the oxidation reaction by creating an alkaline medium that is suitable for it. Gallic acid was used to produce the calibration curves as it is a suitable standard (Louis et al., 2017). To proceed, 200 μL of methanolic extract was mixed with 1 mL of 10% Folin-Ciocalteu solution, mixed and incubated for 4 minutes. After incubation, 800 μL of 7.5% Na_2CO_3 solution was added. The final mixture was shaken and incubated for 2 hours in the dark at room temperature. The absorbance of the resulting blue colored solution was measured at 765 nm using an Optizin 3220 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The blank was prepared in a similar manner except that the sample was replaced by the solvent. The concentration of total polyphenols was calculated from the regression equation of the calibration curve established with the standard, expressed in equivalent micrograms of gallic acid per milligram of extract (mg GAE /g).

Determination of Flavonoid Content

The quantification of flavonoids in the MO oil sample was achieved through AlCl_3 method (Djeridane et al., 2006). For this test, 1 mL of each sample solution as well as the standard prepared in methanol were added to 1 mL of 2% AlCl_3 solution. After ten minutes of incubation in the dark, the absorbance was measured at wavelength of maximum absorption of 510 nm. Triplicates of the experiments were taken to

minimize error. A blank was similarly prepared but void of the sample. The quantification of flavonoids was established with recourse to a linear calibration curve carried out by a quercetin standard at different concentrations from 0 to 450 µg/mL under the same conditions as the sample. The results were expressed in milligrams of quercetin equivalent per gram of extract (mg QE/g).

Determination of Carotenoid Content

The carotenoid content was measured following the method of Sass-Kiss et al., (2005). The results were expressed in mg of β-carotene equivalent (β-CE) per 100 g of sample using the standard curve for β-carotene. In order to realize this, 5 mL of MO oil was dissolved in 20 mL of a composite solvent obtained mixing hexane, acetone and ethanol in the ratio 2:1:1. The mixture was stirred for 30 minutes, left to settle and the upper phase was recovered for absorbance measurement at 450 nm.

Determination of anti-radical activity by DPPH

The 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) method is a standard test used to evaluate antioxidant properties. It is based on measuring the ability of antioxidants to trap the 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazil (DPPH) radical. The latter is a stable radical soluble in methanol or ethanol which has a characteristic absorption at 517 nm giving a violet color. This color changes from violet to yellow when DPPH is reduced to diphenylpicrylhydrazine by a free radical scavenger. The intensity of the color is inversely proportional to the capacity of the antioxidants present in the medium (Sánchez-Moreno, 2002). The DPPH solution was prepared by solubilizing 6 mg of DPPH in 100 mL of methanol. 40 µL of solutions of phenolic extracts or standards were added to 160 µL of DPPH. The mixture was left in the dark for 1 hour and the discoloration compared to the negative control which contains only the DPPH solution was measured at 517 nm. The positive control was represented by ascorbic acid solution as a standard antioxidant. The evaluation of the anti-radical activity using the

DPPH method was expressed as a percentage according to the following relationship:

$$\%Anti - free\ radical\ activity = \left[\frac{(A_{control} - A_{sample})}{A_{control}} \right] \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (7)$$

Infrared Spectroscopic Analysis of *Moringa oleifera* Seed Oil

In order to further investigate the molecular entities of *Moringa oleifera* seed oil, an IR spectrum of the oil sample was taken using the Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectrophotometer (FT-IR), the Bio-Rad Excalibur Model FTS3000MX in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹.

GC-MS Analysis of *Moringa oleifera* Oil

Analysis by direct introduction of fatty acids into the column is possible, but generally these substances have fairly high melting points, while their methyl esters are much more volatile. Therefore, methylation was first carried out which permitted will working at a lower temperature and using polar phases which could not withstand too high a temperature. This analysis made available the fatty acid content of MO oil.

Result and Discussions

Oil Extraction Yield from *Moringa oleifera* (MO) Seeds

The extraction of oil from MO seeds by the mechanical press method gave a yield of 26.07%. This result is higher than that obtained by Louni (2009) which is 16.16% using similar extraction method. This can be explained by the fact that the oil content of *Moringa oleifera* seeds varies depending on the geographical area (Alang, 2019). Oil yield through mechanical methods is also a function of the pressure exercised by the press. However, the MO oil yield gotten in this work is much lower than that obtained through solvent extraction using hexane which gave 41.16% (Omaji et al., 2018). This is explained by the fact that in mechanical expression, all oil

molecules are seldom squeezed out by the press while it is possible for the solvent to dissolve out all oil molecules in the sample during solvent extraction provided sufficient extraction time is allowed.

Results of Physico-Chemical Characterization of MO Oil

Properties of *Moringa oleifera* Oil

Table 1. Physico-Chemical Characteristics of Moringa Oil

Parameters	Values	
Physical Parameters	Density (g/mL)	0.896
	Refractive index at 20°C	1.468
	Viscosity (mPa.s)	49.80± 0.30
Chemical Parameters	Acid value (%)	2.69
	Peroxide value (meqO ₂ per kg oil)	3.7
	Saponification number (mgKOH/g oil)	189.34
	Iodine number (g/100g oil)	67.79

Table 1 gives the results of physico-chemical analysis of MO seeds oil. From the table, the density of MO seeds oil is 0.896 g/mL. The density helps us to classify oil as light or heavy oil. It is also considered as purity indicator which can indicate the presence of impurities. The density of an oil may vary depending on the degree of unsaturation, oxidation and polymerization of the oil. The value obtained here (0.89 g/mL) is in the range of literature values (0.896 – 0.910mg/mL) as reported by Foidl et al., (2001). The refractive index obtained in this work is 1.468. From this value, our MO oil may be classified as a semi-drying and non-drying fatty substance. This is in conformity with Tshiombe (2011), who stated that drying oils at 20°C, have refractive indices in the range 1.480 to 1.523 while half-drying oils have refractive indices between 1.470 and 1.476 and non-drying oils have refractive indices between 1.468 and 1.470. The value gotten in this study is slightly higher than that obtained by Foidl et al., (2001) (1.46). The viscosity of an oil is a measure of its resistance to flow. It is inversely proportional to temperature. The value obtained here for MO

was 49.8 ± 0.3 mPa.s. The viscosity of oil may influence its applications.

The acid number is a vital factor in evaluating the stability of an oil at room temperature. It indicates and quantifies free fatty acids present in the oil which also indicates the degree of degradation of oil molecules. Hence the acid number of an oil is purity parameter. In this work the acid number complies with the standard given by the Codex Alimentarius (2015). The value here (2.26) is slightly lower than that of Abdulkarim et al., (2005) (2.48) but higher than that of Zhao et al., (2019) (0.24). This slight variation may be due to extraction methods, storage, and effects of geographical location of Moringa trees. In general, the acid number of oils increases with storage time due to the oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids under the influence of light and oxygen (Tchiégang et al., 2004).

The peroxide value helps to indicate the extent of oxidation of unsaturated fatty acids in oil. The higher the value, the more deteriorated the oil is. The peroxide value obtained in this study (3.7mgKOH/g) falls in the range recommended by Codex Alimentarius standard (2015) with maximum value 10mgKOH/g. But this value is slightly higher than those reported by Zhao et al., (2019) which was 1.69mgKOH/g. The saponification number of an oil sample is a function of the chain length of the fatty acids constituting the oil. The saponification number is inversely proportional to the chain lengths of fatty acid moieties in the oil. The saponification number also allows us to calculate the average molar mass of the fatty acids making up an oil sample. The saponification value of MO oil obtained in this research (189.34) conforms to that earlier obtained by Zhao et al., (2019) (189.6mgKOH/g) but lower than the value of Adejumo et al., (2013) (252.34mgKOH/g) and similar to that of olive oil which falls between 184 to 196 mg of KOH/g. Hence MO seed oil may be considered a light oil containing short-chain fatty acids (Louni, 2009).

The iodine number is proportional to the degree of unsaturation of an oil sample. An oil sample with a low iodine value would have a low content

of unsaturated fatty acids with attendant reduced reactivity of the glyceride moieties to polymerization, thermal oxidation and related reactions of rancidity. A low iodine value also implies better storage stability (Alang et al., 2018). The iodine number from this study is 67.79g/100g which is slightly higher than the result of Zhao et al., (2019) who got 66.54g/100g and lower than the value of Adejumo et al., (2013) who obtained 72.40g/100g of oil. The value is lower than that of olive oil which varies between 75 and 94 g/100 g of oil; this indicates that *Moringa oleifera* oil is to a lesser extent unsaturated.

Titration Results of Total phenols, Flavonoids and Carotenoids

The quantitative determination of total polyphenols was carried out by the Folin-Ciocalteu colorimetric method using gallic acid as a standard. The quantity of total polyphenols in the oil sample of *Moringa oleifera* analyzed gave 9.7 mg GAE/g of oil was calculated from the equation generated by the calibration curve given as:

$$y = 7.01 \times 1010^{-2}x - 3.52 \times 10^{-2} \text{ and } R^2 = 0.9915 \quad (8)$$

mgGAE/g = mg of Galic Acid Equivalent/gram of oil

This result is higher than that of Baye-Niwah et al., (2020) which was 7.8 mgGAE/g of oil. Hence MO oil obtained in this study may be richer in polyphenolic content. The rich content of polyphenols in MO seed oil confers antioxidant and antibacterial properties to the oil and makes it a good agent for possible use in cosmetic and pharmaceutical preparation.

The determination of total flavonoids was carried out using the AlCl₃ colorimetric method (Chang et al., 2002) using quercetin as a standard. The flavonoid content of the *Moringa Oleifera* oil sample analyzed corresponds to 66.4 mg QE/g of oil was determined using the equation generated by the quercetin calibration curve given as:

$$y = 2.3 \times 10^{-3}x + 4.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ with } R^2 = 0.99 \quad (9)$$

This result is higher than that of Baye-Niwah et al., (2020) which was 17.1 mgQE/g of oil.

Flavonoids are rich in phenolic compounds which in turn possess antioxidant and antibacterial properties. The presence of these flavonoids in *Moringa oleifera* seed oils is thus highly solicited for its plausible coveted use in cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications (Alessandro et al., 2016).

The carotenoid content of the sample of MO oil analyzed corresponds to 0.25 mg/mL was determined from the equation generated by the calibration curve of beta-carotene:

$$y=6.397x \text{ with } R^2=0.9986 \quad (10)$$

This suggests a relatively low content of carotenoids in MO seed oil.

Results of Antioxidant Activity by Free Radical Scavenging using DPPH

DPPH is characterized by its ability to produce stable free radicals. The presence of these DPPH• radicals give rise to a dark violet color of solution, which absorbs at around 517 nm. The reduction of DPPH radicals by an antioxidant agent results in color intensity reduction of the solution.

Activity of MO Seed Oil compared to a Standard

The graph above shows us the inhibitory activities of vitamin C and Moringa oil depending on the DPPH concentration. The curve of vitamin C is above that of Moringa oil implying that vitamin C has elevated anti radical potency. The concentration of vitamin C capable of inhibiting 50% of free radicals (IC₅₀) is thus lower than that of MO seed oil. The antiradical power of a substance is inversely proportional to the IC₅₀ value of that substance. The greater the IC₅₀ value, the less effective the substance shall be as an antiradical. Hence the MO seed oil can

be used for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications due to its potent antiradical and antibacterial properties (Alessandro et al., 2016).

Figure 1. Anti-Radical Activity Curve

IR Analysis of MO

The infrared spectrum of MO seed oil is shown by figure 5. The esters have characteristically strong absorption bands due to carbonyl (C=O) at $1750 - 1730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and that of C-O at $1300 - 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Guillen and Cabo, 1997 ; Soares et al., 2008). Stretching vibrations of CH_3 occur at $2980 - 2950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, those of the CH_2 groups appear at $2950 - 2850 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. For saturated esters, the absorption bands of C-C, C=O and C-O bond occur between 1230 and 1160 cm^{-1} . The absorption peaks of MO oil shown in Figure 5 include peak 1 at 3734.73 cm^{-1} for free OH groups on the glycerol backbone. The ester group is confirmed by peak 6 at 1743.73 cm^{-1} and peak 7 at 1160.25 cm^{-1} . Then the presence of CH_2 by the band at 2853.68 cm^{-1} and the CH - group on the glycerol backbone is represented by peak 3 at 3009.35 cm^{-1} . The broad absorption band between $1300 \text{ cm}^{-1} - 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirms the numerous C-O bonds in oil samples.

Figure 2. Infrared Spectrum of Moringa oleifera Seed Oil

Table 2. Fatty acid profile of Moringa oleifera seed Oil.

Names	Retention Time	Percentage content (%)
Myristic Acid (C14 : 0)	17,1	0,18
Palmitic Acid (C16 :0)	18,77	7,35
Margaric Acid (C17 :0)	19,30	0,05

Stearic Acid (C18 : 0)	20,213	6,14
Oleic Acid (C18 :1) ω 9	21,38	76,45
Trans Oleic Acid (C18 :1 t)	21,56	0,60
Linoleic Acid (C18 :2) ω 6	22,218	0,84
Arachidic Acid (C20 : 0)	2,301	3,07
Gadoleic Acid (C 20 : 1)	28,070	2,65
Behenic Acid (C22 : 0)	30,62	4,25

The total amount of saturated fatty acids identified in MO seed oil include; myristic acid (C 14:0), palmitic acid (C16:0), margaric acid (C17:0), stearic acid (C 18:0), arachidic acid (C 20:0) and behenic acid (C 22:0). The saturated fatty acids in *Moringa oleifera* oil from this study is 21.04%, and the predominant acid is Palmitic Acid (C16:0). Moringa oil is a very good source of unsaturated fatty acids with a content of around 82.54% of which oleic acid (C18:1) is the predominant unsaturated fatty acid with a percentage content of 76.45%. This acid is known for its superior stability and its high nutritional value for the body and for the skin. This last result allows Moringa oil to be classified in the category of oleic oils (Zhao et al., 2019) and very useful for pharmaceutical and cosmetic applications (Idris et al., 2020).

Conclusion

In this study, *Moringa oleifera* oil was extracted by mechanical expression with a yield of 26.07%. The physico-chemical parameters show that the oil is light and pure. The MO seed oil has desirable for cosmetic and pharmaceutical applications due to the presence of polyphenolic and flavonoids compounds which possess antimicrobial activities. Hence the MO seed oil can play the role of a bioactive ingredient when used in food supplements, pharmaceutical substances and cosmetic preparations to boost public health. Furthermore, the MO seed oil due to its low acid value renders it a candidate for green energy production like biodiesel through conversion technologies like transesterification amongst others.

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